

THE STRESS INTENSITY FACTORS AND INTERACTIONS OF MULTIPLE INCLINED CRACKS IN A COMPOSITE LAMINATE

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ABSTRACT

Intralaminar transverse cracks are usually the first sign of damage of fibre-reinforced multidirectional composite laminates. Many studies are devoted to the effect of transverse cracks in fibre-reinforced composite laminates on the properties of the laminates and the multiple crack interactions [1, 2], but these studies are dedicated to the cracks that are with identical length and perpendicular to the interfaces. It is noted that when composite laminates are under transverse shear or impact, inclined cracks with different lengths may appear in the laminates. In this paper, the stress intensity factors at the tips of an isolated and inclined crack, and two neighbouring cracks with different lengths which are embedded in the central layer of a $[\pm\theta^\circ/90^\circ]$ angle-ply composite laminate when subjected to tensile loading are solved by the Fourier integral transform method [3] combined with the superposition principle [2]. The relationships between the stress intensity factors and the geometrical parameters of the laminate, including the thickness of the outer constraining sublaminates, ply angle θ° , crack orientation angle and crack spacing, are explored. The results show that when the thickness of the outer constraining sublaminates is more than twice that of the central layer, the influence of the thickness of the outer constraining sublaminates on the stress intensity factor is negligible. It is interesting that for an angle-ply composite laminate containing an isolated crack with a fixed crack length, although the influences of the ply angle θ° and the crack orientation angle on the stress intensity factors are significant, the ratio of the stress intensity factor under mode II to that under mode I stays almost the same as the crack orientation angle varies. We also examine the interaction effect among multiple cracks under a mixed I-II mode based on the stress intensity factors and the generalized maximum tangential stress (MTS) criterion considering the effect of both the stress intensity factors and the T-stress [4], and find that the longer crack dominates the stress concentration when the two crack lengths are significantly different. The crack shielding effect becomes stronger while the crack spacing decreases, which means that it is almost impossible for the shorter crack to propagate when the crack spacing is very small.

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